

EXPLORING DIMENSIONS OF SUSTAINABLE DESIGN WITHIN THE ARCHITECTURAL CURRICULUM

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Abstract

This paper presents the efforts of the faculty of the Department of Architecture of the University of Nicosia to introduce principles of sustainability, as those pertain to the architecture and design, to an undergraduate, accredited program of architectural studies. Sustainability as a concept and as a practice is examined through a variety of social, economic and environmental attributes, and is imparted to the students as a theoretical premise and as practical extension. The means by which sustainability is injected into the curriculum is the Sustainable Design Unit, the specifics of which are described, examined and evaluated in this paper.

Introduction

Twenty years ago, principles and practice of sustainable architecture were rarely included or pursued within conventional academic curricula. The most likely explanation for that phenomenon was that the practice of sustainable architecture was considered by most academics and non-academics alike, as a fad. The transition from fad to fashion and from fashion to necessity was instigated by the energy crisis which acquired the public's attention in the 1970's, the repercussions of which have been escalating dramatically ever since.

Necessity or not, a large number of academic institutions teaching architecture do not imbed environmental agendas into the design culture they promote. It must, of course, be noted that effective, environmentally responsible architectural design does not require striking labels such as "ecological design," "green buildings," or "sustainable architecture." In fact, the frequency of use of these terms in a casual conscience increases the risk of their losing the impact of their intended meaning.

In 2009, the University of Nicosia, in a sober attempt to stay in tune with progress and global shifts in development, introduced a unique direction for its fourth-year students: a branch of study, titled Sustainable Design Unit. Instead of a conventional thesis preparatory year of academic studies followed by the fifth year where the thesis project is to be generated, the faculty created two Units – one being the Sustainable Design Unit - from which students entering their fourth year would choose. Each Unit has a distinct area of concentration which is expressed within the framework of its related studio course.

A crucial argument that transpires from the placement of this paper is whether environmentally responsible architecture should be regarded as specialisation within the architectural education or whether the entire spectrum of architecture should be taught as a science and as an art that is equally accountable to man and to the environment. This begs the question, shouldn't architecture always be ecologically responsible? This matter, however, will not be examined within the context of this paper.

Description of Sustainable Design Unit

In addition to the studio studies, each Unit is comprised of two supplementary courses where students are exposed to theoretical and technical issues associated with Unit. The two courses supplementing the Sustainable Design Unit are 'History and Theory of Sustainable Architecture' and 'Sustainable Design Practices.' The History and Theory course offers a comprehensive understanding of the principles of sustainable architecture within a historical and socio-political context, whereas the Sustainable Design

Practices course provides the necessary technical knowledge and mechanics to succeed towards sustainable architecture and construction.

The faculty members undertaking responsibilities within the Unit are strictly selected for their expertise, knowledge and experience in the Unit's area of study. In cases where no faculty member in the particular area of expertise was available, adjunct faculty was hired in a concerted attempt to maintain the highest standard of education within the Units. Regardless of which studio course the students are registered to, they are expected to follow all supplementary courses offered by both Units. This achieves a much-needed balance and uniformity among fourth-year studies. The studio course is a two-year commitment on behalf of both students and faculty. By their fifth-year, students are expected to have developed, expanded or isolated their fourth-year studio studies which will promote them to a successful thesis.

Sustainable Design Unit: the Studio Course

The studio course offered within the Sustainable Design Unit is titled 'Exploring Dimensions of Slow Life Filtered through Sustainable Design.' It was determined that the concept of slowness be added to studio thematic as a filtering device or mechanism because of its unique adaptability to grand notions as well as to modest ones.

Slowness, whether of living or of design, is an intriguing concept whose elusive nature encourages creative thought and sets numerous sceptical filters benefitting good design. Identifying, observing and evaluating slow life raises issues of perception on time and accountability to nature in ways that are intrinsic to sustainable design. Slow life is primarily concerned with the analysis and reading of architectural dimensions as a conceptual framework for the presentation of significantly new, original and meaningful architectural ideas. The studio explores the theoretical, the philosophical, the physical and the aesthetic qualities of *slowness* from life to architecture, their potential for making space and the emotional capacity of the spaces they make.

Conceptual Ideas

The following thoughts, expressed in a stream of consciousness, act as springboards for the foundation of the Studio's philosophy. In turn, these questions become the impetus for an entire set of other issues requiring students to investigate interpretations of slow life and fast life within the context of sustainable architecture. However, in order to progress successfully to this level of investigation, each student is first encouraged to develop his or her own idea of what sustainability means. Students are urged to regard sustainability as a means of survival, both social and environmental, whose viability is directly linked to economic, social and ecological parameters.

Waking up late... rushing to get dressed... no time for breakfast... darting to the car or to the bus station... getting to work and then, rushing towards this and towards that... and then rushing some more...

What makes our life rush by so fast, what compels us to always be on the run? What inner need provides us with this momentum? Is it the need to compete, to achieve, to succeed?

Is the applied frequency emitted by our built environment subliminally feeding our impulse to rush?

We eat fast food, think fast thoughts, talk quickly to our friends and colleagues and inevitably, we create environments to match the fast rhythms of our lives.

We live fast lives and it is indeed quite likely that we design the appropriate architectural elements to accommodate our fast paces.

Take a moment and stand still:

Does food taste different when you chew while standing still? Does the ground under your feet feel softer? Does your breath feel cooler, stronger when taken in slowly and released slower still?

How does it feel to live slowly and enjoy all flavours of life? Savouring rather than devouring? Walking rather than running? Observing rather than judging?

Is slow life a virtue that can be identified within western lifestyle? Does it need to be juxtaposed to fast life for it to have a discernable meaning? How does sustainable living compare to slow and to fast living?

Does architecture have a measurable speed? How do we feel about the speed of our surrounding architecture? Can we identify slow and fast paces in our built environment?

Philosophical Premise

Let us try to playfully visualize all-things-architectural to be the product of a specific muscle group in the designer's subconscious. The muscle group is comprised of other smaller muscles which we can identify as "creativity," "practicality," "technical accuracy," etc. We can visualize the muscle at its earliest appearance in the subconscious mind, while it is still somewhat atrophied. Upon attending architecture school, the muscle is exercised and gradually starts functioning as a unit, all members flexing and contracting in unison producing a well-shaped, efficient muscle. Sustainable design and environmental responsibility should, in theory, appear in the designer's subconscious as members of this "architectural" muscle group and together they have the potential to make the muscle stronger, more efficient and more resilient.

Since in the case of the Department of Architecture of the University of Nicosia, studies focusing on sustainable design officially enter the curriculum for the first time in the fourth year, regarding the principles of sustainability as part of the muscle group mentioned above may not be a realistic vision. In the course of a five year educational programme, it is probably safe to assume that the synergistic members of this muscle group have already been exercised into a shape by working together with method and system and any attempt for alterations may be met with resistance or with less than adequate results.

Consequently, the purpose of this studio and the philosophical quest supporting the Sustainable Design Unit as a whole, given the circumstances of the Unit's conception, is not to enforce sustainable design and environmental responsibility as surrogate members of the muscle group. The purpose here is for these two principles to be the primary forces that help shape the muscle to fitness. They are not to be regarded as muscles, part of a larger unit of body, but as the weights, the dumbbells if you will, the design muscle is trained with in order to become more capable and resourceful. A timelier introduction of sustainable issues into the department's curriculum may be a more beneficial investment in the future of environmental culture in architecture schools, but such adaptations require time, patience and perseverance on behalf of academics and administrators alike.

Practical Extensions

On a more tangible level, the mission of the studio is to elevate architecture and design to a coexistence of a harmonious and productive synergy of man, nature and the spirit of place. At the end of the studio journey, the students should be in a position to face their architectural identity in such a way where sustainable design will not represent an attachment or a supplement to their design principles, but both entities operate as an integrated process.

At the start of the studio journey, a foundation needs to be set where all attempts to define sustainability are put on the table and theories are taken into consideration. The global, multifaceted nature of sustainability is presented in such a way that students become aware of its ever-elusive definition and the range of disciplines it involves. This realization is inevitably faced by the students with some trepidation, so time is set aside for individual consultations helping students identify their own niche within the network of possibilities of sustainable design.

Sustainability is expressed not only as a sound building technique but as a deep socio-political issue that transcends generations, race and social class. The studio projects themselves, aim to explore the interdependency of issues of environmental, social and economic sustainability where students are prompted to develop individual, critical positions regarding the broad concept of sustainability and to extend and explore those positions through their architectural design process.

Studio Specifics

Assessment Methods

At the beginning of each semester, students are given a course outline containing the class syllabus, attendance and grading policy. Projects and exercises are assigned to students each semester and their duration may range from one, two or three weeks, depending on the nature of the project. Although the number of projects assigned in the first semester may vary, the second semester is always the focus of a single project study. The fifth year is dedicated exclusively to the generation of a single, thesis project.

Each students' grade is then determined by the maturity of problem analysis, research work, thinking process, creative generation of ideas, methods and methodology, application of mixed media skills, quality of final product, progress and attendance (see assessment criteria). Attendance is also taken into account as well as lecture and tutorial participation.

Assessment Criteria

Problem analysis

Initially, the students are expected to develop a range of ideas, rather than a single concept, that demonstrate a creative response to the brief of the studio course. Within the framework of the assigned brief, the students are to identify the nature and the requirements of the task at hand, irrespective of whether the tasks are determined by the brief or whether they are self-generated. Tasks must be prioritized and any limitations imposed by the assignment must be taken into account. The students are expected to provide full consideration of any intended audience of their work. In extension, they are expected to be in a position to identify and communicate problems and solutions in an appropriate matter. The proposed solutions must demonstrate a clear and purposeful initiative to the identified problems.

Research

Students are expected to apply an enquiring approach to identify a range of visual and textual sources, evaluate the information gathered and proceed with appropriate selection. Within this process, students must demonstrate the ability to synthesize different types of visual and contextual information and to reveal how research has informed the project's progress.

Conceptual development and generation of ideas

Research will initiate and explore creative proposals as well as act as a vehicle to explore and develop a range of ideas that demonstrate a creative response to the research question as it is derived from the brief. Students are expected to foster links between their research, ideas and the intended audience.

Working methods

As with every academic assignment, students are advised to plan their time efficiently and to complete tasks with time to spare for review by fellow students and members of the faculty. The studio course also encourages working in groups thus promoting skills in leadership and cooperation. Working in groups also helps students identify their personal strengths and weaknesses.

Application of media skills

Students, who deal with their academic work maturely, will be able to develop the appropriate technical and manipulative skills to support the production of their project. They should also be able to demonstrate creativity in use of materials and methods as well as recognize and build on their individual strengths.

Quality of final product (visual, written and oral presentation)

The quality of the presentations is important and it should aspire to be as high of standard as possible. The visual and aesthetic impact must demonstrate the connection between the finished work, the original idea and the intended audience.

Any written work to be submitted during the two-year course of the studio course must be presented as articulately as possible, with coherent arguments and it must speak of the views and values earned during the research. Students are encouraged to continuously review their written work, as this is the only way to strive towards improvement.

Although oral presentations can be a nerve-wrecking experience, clarity and succinctness are of the essence. The students are encouraged during studio time to constantly practice their oral argument in order to achieve the best possible result.

Studio Description and Pedagogical Methods

Site Selection

The studio course of the Sustainable Design Unit places particular focus on site analysis, as this is a crucial tool in exercising good bioclimatic principles. After the initial influx of new information regarding the philosophy, mechanics and application of sustainable architecture, the students need a means to feel grounded. For this reason, the first order of business is to establish familiarity with the proposed site and with the climatic and geographical circumstances that are specific to it. In the first year of its inception, the studio site was a national park within the capital city of Nicosia. Since then, it has since been decided that students who are in their fourth and fifth year or studies ought to be allowed to make their individual choices on site. Site must be wisely chosen so that it lends itself as a suitable platform for the students to investigate their personal interests.

The students of the studio are expected to develop their own brief – a good preparation for their self-directed thesis investigation, which will follow in their fifth year of studies. Students, in groups and individually, are called to examine their site in its entirety and to uncover its layers of complexity and potential. Shortcomings of the site are scrutinized and discussed in a productive and educational environment, while case studies are used to offer depth and perspective. Site analysis should produce a series of overlays pertaining to basic analytical issues such as land use, fauna and flora, circulation, geology and topography. Emphasis is placed on intuitive interpretations of site and conceptual models expressing those readings are encouraged.

Since this is the first contact some students experience with site analysis of this scale, they are encouraged to review the work of Ian McHarg and James LaGro. Once students are comfortable with their site's particulars, they are called to develop a masterplan responding to an appropriate scheme of development. This masterplan will serve them for the entirety of the year, since all their subsequent building interventions will be based on it.

Assignments

Throughout the three years of its existence, the studio course of the Sustainable Design Unit has attempted two separate approaches regarding assignment briefs. In the first year of the studio's inception, in 2009, students were required to complete a series of projects which had a distinct duration ranging from two to three weeks, depending on the size of the project and the overall student workload. Students were encouraged to approach these projects as charrettes and work under rigid deadlines.

Briefly, the semester began with the analysis of site, then the generation of a masterplan of appropriate and thematic uses. Each student is expected to develop his or her own thematic park based on his or her individual evaluation of the site's shortcomings, community needs and environmental betterment. The students chose a theme that is a challenge to them; one which they hope will lead them somewhere they have not been before. Students' individual tasks include exploration of thematic dimensions of the concepts of *slow* and *fast* (keeping notes, drawings, samples, cut-outs and anything else appropriate) research and peer presentation on their chosen theme.

Following the masterplan, students were called to design a series of resting points whose location had already be determined in the masterplan. The resting points, intended as a spot where the park's visitors can take a break, represent the students' first attempt at a structure that follows basic principles of sustainable design. The design of the resting point structure must be such that it can be erected or installed at any point in the park, but can be adaptable and responsive to the particular location it is intended for. The concept driving its design must be related to the park's proposed theme and must be consistent with the findings of the investigation of *slow*. The structure's area must not exceed 10m² and all passive and active solar design principles must be applied. The prototype must be responsive to climate, wind, sun and other particulars of the site and it must offer protection from the rain. Material investigation and selection is crucial.

The second and third project must be a structure of 50-100m² and 500m² respectively. Choice of materials must be dealt with more perseverance, bringing forth topics such as material longevity, potential toxicity, recycling and reusing. Energy-saving technology is investigated as well as other established technologies demonstrating the principles of sustainable architecture and construction. In the 500m² structure the challenge of designing sustainably is now elevated to include architectural concerns such as access, entrance, space-use hierarchy, accommodation of auxiliary spaces, circulation and aesthetic acceptance within the natural landscape. Issues of cross-ventilation, orientation and exposure to natural sunlight are now examined more rigorously.

In the second semester of that year (2010), the final structure addressed was a semester-long project of a more complex building structure responding to issues of site specify and sustainable design. Before addressing their intervention, whether that is a building or a complex of buildings, the students were assigned an exercise to affectionately known as "site reconnaissance." This exercise is intended to bring students physically and intellectually close to the site of their proposed intervention. They were required to section their proposed site to a grid where each square has the approximate dimensions of 2mX2m. Then the students are called to investigate and document each grid as a microcosm, isolating particular characteristics present in most of the grids and proposing a possible hierarchy. Through this exercise the students are encouraged to develop their own language of reading the landscape of their site. Their findings are then presented in class in the form of a conceptual model, stationary or interactive, or in two-dimensional images.

For the academic year which began in the Fall 2010 and was completed in the Spring 2011, the Unit's faculty collectively decided to forgo the series of projects and to allow fourth-year students to carry out their studio study in similar fashion to the fifth-year students. Fifth-year thesis students begin their final year by identifying a thesis question, then proceeded to accumulate literature to support their thesis quest and produce a consummate research paper presented with appropriate bibliographical notations. Thesis projects should differ from fourth-year projects in their complexity of concepts and design and in depth of investigation.

Lectures, Guests and Reviews

Developing an understanding of design, maintenance and operation of the built environment while minimizing energy needs, is a strong component of the Studio's objectives. These issues are presented to students through a series of in-studio lectures by faculty members, expert guests, recent graduates and other students. Presentations are based on theory, case studies, technological advances and social issues. The basic framework of sustainable architecture, such as theory, ecology and technology is also offered to the students through the two supplementary courses they take as part of their fourth-year curriculum.

The studio of the Sustainable Design Unit fosters a culture of diversity of opinion and constructive criticism. Throughout the duration of the studio year, a series of guest lecturers and critics offer their time and advice to individual students, evaluating each project's merits, providing intriguing stimuli, feedback and helping each student elevate his or her work to the next level. All desk reviews with guest lecturers are done in the presence of at least one of the regular studio instructors to better communicating class objectives and to facilitate communication.

Guest critics have included artists specializing on ecosystems, practicing architects focusing on bioclimatics and digital design, and professors of relevant subjects from other local universities. Through their diverse educational background, the guest critics, some of whom studied and worked in countries such as Germany, Spain, Holland, England, USA and Greece, were also in a position to offer unique pedagogical perspectives.

Most studio days begin with a pinup of each student's work and his or her work is being discussed earnestly and constructively by fellow students and the instructors. As with all studios at University of Nicosia, there is a mid-semester review for all students where the entire faculty is invited as well as guest critics from other universities and professionals. These reviews prove to be an excellent means of coordinating progress in all same-year studios and they provide an opportunity for students to benefit from the experience of a large scale presentation.

As mentioned in greater detail above, students are assessed on the level of concentration they exhibit, their rigour and tenacity. Their subsequent grade is determined by the maturity with which they tackle problem analysis, the depth and commitment of their research work, the clarity of their thinking process, their creativity in generating ideas, application of mixed media skills, the quality of final product, progress and attendance.

Lessons Learnt from Studio Course for the Academic Year 2009-2010

The work presented by most students at the end of the 2009 academic year was of a particularly high standard and earned high praise from university faculty and colleagues from abroad. The ultimate success of the studio depends on engaging all students, irrespective of their academic background and individual accomplishments and shortcomings. With this in mind, the instructors of the studio course identified certain issues with regards the studio curriculum that required revisiting.

The idea of completing four projects, those being the masterplan, resting points and two structures of varying dimensions ranged from challenging to practically unattainable, especially for transfer students whose background studies did not conform entirely to those of other students from the University of Nicosia. In fact, by the end of the academic year 2009-2010, all transfer students chose to withdraw from the studio course shortly before the end-of-year review.

Students were advised to complete each of the individual projects in the finite time assigned, present it, then move on to the next project. Based on the comments collected during the review, the students were expected to improve on their own time the project that just been reviewed, in time for the final review. This proved a difficult task to coordinate, particularly for the transfer students, who seemed to be juggling more balls than the other students.

The curriculum for the forthcoming (academic year 2010-2011) fourth-year students was thus altered to include one project in the course of the first semester instead of four. This structure must be habitable and must follow a rigorous process of well-documented research and adhere to principles of sustainable design, it must be site-specific and climate-responsive. Students were encouraged to produce a structure of approximately 300m². The second semester curriculum did not undergo significant changes.

As mentioned before, another significant alteration in the academic year 2010-2011 was the absence of site. The national park which had served as studio site for the previous academic year, was forced to be abandoned because students who were keen in carrying out strictly urban investigations were unable to pursue their interest. This adjustment inevitably brought forth discontinuity in group site analyses. However, the instructors attempted to compensate by offering individual guidance to each student with respect to how to best analyse their chosen site.

Lessons Learnt from Studio Course for the Academic Year 2010-2011

Taking to heart all lesson learnt in the previous academic year and looking forward to implementing the new curriculum, the academic year of 2010-2011 commenced. This academic year marks the first year of fifth year thesis projects. As such, it was decided that fourth-year studio students would merge with fifth-year thesis studio, within the Sustainable Design Unit. In fact, students attending studio in their fourth and fifth year share the same premises, studio times, instructors, lectures and workshops. The students from both years benefit greatly from each other's presence and momentum. The fifth year students are, of course, not obligated to attend the structured curriculum of the fourth-years, but those who did, found themselves in an overall advantageous position regarding to exposure on relevant topics and peer review.

The fifth year is devoted entirely to the development of a major design project, self-initiated and based on a strong sense of professionalism and design maturity. Students of the fifth year are encouraged to take further their architectural, cultural and theoretical preoccupations and test their architectural imagination. Students are expected to use their so far obligatory experience of different design, constructional and structural models and their aesthetic properties to choose aptly and with sensibility from the full range of possibilities. Individual guidance and recommendation of specific readings are given according to the students' chosen topic. Main concerns are research methods, study and analysis of design works and projects, appropriate presentation techniques, concept presentation, structural detailing and model making.

Lessons Learnt from Studio Course for the Academic Year 2011-2012

As the second year producing thesis students, academic year 2011-2012 proved to be an important barometer for the effectiveness of the course. Thesis students were allowed more autonomy in time management issues and more emphasis was set on the written research fifth-year students had to prepare in lieu of their design project. The research the students undertake is directly related to their thesis project, and although they attend a compulsory thesis seminar with students from other Units, the Sustainable Design Unit studio instructors kept a close eye on the progress of the written part of thesis. The written thesis was due for submission at the end of the first semester and an unfortunate consequence that transpired was while students worked on the literary part of their research, they maintained a rather passive attitude towards their studio work. More visual imagery relating to the literary research should have been requested. This was an oversight on behalf of the instructors that will not be repeated.

Also, fourth-year studio students were encouraged to follow a schedule similar to the fifth-years, with a written thesis to support their chosen area of interest. Although this proved to be a good strategy to better prepare them for their fifth year, less time was spent on design work. In the years to follow, the Unit's studio will aim to offer more guidance on matters of allocation of time.

Conclusions and Future Improvements

If the degree of success of the studio course of the Unit of Sustainable Unit is measured by students' enthusiasm, then the studio has surely been a triumph. During the course of two years taught, the students gradually became committed to the studio's culture, as evidenced by the quality of their finished product, the degree of collaboration inspired among the group and the close bond fostered between the students and the instructors. Although the Unit extracts particularly hard work and dedication, a number of students who were not originally assigned to it, have consistently been requesting to transfer to it.

A diversity of thematic projects were taken on such as skate board and cycling facilities, urban safety, sustainable historic restoration, a dog park, a performance park, an educational centre, etc. A variety of subjects were tackled, including modularity, appropriate water purification technology, flexible occupancy and space reuse and issues of embodied energy. The studio's standards were kept at a constantly challenging level and as a result, small number of students who were not able to keep up had to withdraw. Although all help was made available to them, the students decided on their own accord that they had more to gain by repeating the studio year.

The students were not only able to produce mature projects touching on all basic issues proclaimed by the studio agenda, but most of them were able to greatly improve on their overall ability to solve complex architectural spaces and successfully present them in professional drawings and impressive computer renderings. This was partly the result of the instructors' perseverance and insistence that students should be handled as adults who are but a heartbeat away from professional employment.

An improvement the studio will be striving towards in future years is to keep the slow life parameter closer and more apparent in the studio process. Some students' research on slow life, regardless of how thoroughly it was initially executed, stayed in embryonic stages and was overshadowed by more tangible concerns such as those derived from sustainable architecture. Conversely, one student opted to view slow life as a product of comparison and took on a project focussing on fast life. This was a welcome extension of the *slow* investigation and showed healthy initiative and creativity.

The studio of the Sustainable Design Unit has not only a prolific course for students and a valuable experience for the instructors; it proved to be a useful platform for discussion regarding pedagogical targets and techniques for fourth-year studios at the University of Nicosia. Since the completion of the 2012 academic year, the university's faculty has been using the knowledge and lessons learnt from the studio as guidance in the objectives and planning of future studios. More importantly, the students' high level of product has become a datum on which students' projects are now being evaluated.

Student Work

As a means of further exhibiting the studio's achievements, the two-year progress of a Unit student is presented (Figures 9.1-9.5). Name of student: Alexandros Postekkis

Title of 1st year Unit Work: Awakenning the Senses

Title of 2nd year Unit Work and Thesis Project: Incremental Revitalization of Abandoned Industrial Buildings

Figure 9.1 Resting Point considered through vision and hearing: Two entrances are created according to existing paths, as a welcoming gesture. The axis leads to the heart of the enclosure where sensations are expected to be heightened.

Figure 9.2 The Experience Route: This structure is situated in on an area of high vegetation in order to synthesize to proper environment that will enhance the sense of touch, taste and smell. These senses are triggered through a series of events experienced through the path's route.

Figure 9.3 Multifunctional Center: The project's intention is to incorporate two kinds of paths. A path intended to heighten two senses is combined with a path of the three senses. The communion of both synthesize a building.

Figure 9.4 Exhibition Structure: Shifting between the visitor's perception of fast and slow

Figure 9.5 Thesis Project: Incremental Revitalization of Abandoned Industrial Buildings
The project explores the incremental transformation of abandoned industrial buildings attempting to activate and reintegrate these structures in the socioeconomic system according to emerging needs of the industry. Through examples like the Duisburg Park as well as important conceptual theories of strategic reuse, the proposed building will undergo a gradual transition of total transformation whilst maintaining the memory of former use and significance. The aim of this project is to promote a smooth transition from the building's previous use to its new function by always maintaining a piece of "memory" of function. Through this reuse of space, a sustainable strategy arises, where cost efficiency and recycling of an existing structure through awakening building's and people's memory, becomes a focus of design development.

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